

AN ENERGY RATE APPROACH FOR OPTIMIZED FREQUENCY SELECTION FOR REPRODUCIBLE FATIGUE ASSESSMENT OF COMPOSITES

Daniel Hülsbusch¹, Andreas Kohl¹, Selim Mrzljak¹, Ulrich Fehrenbacher², Jürgen Emig², Patrick Striemann³, Michael Niedermeier³ and Frank Walther¹

¹ Department of Materials Test Engineering (WPT), TU Dortmund University, Dortmund, Germany, daniel.huelsbusch@tu-dortmund.de, www.wpt-info.de

² Rühl Puromer GmbH, Friedrichsdorf, Germany, ulrich.fehrenbacher@ruehl-ag.com, www.ruehl-ag.de

³ Laboratory of Material Testing, University of Applied Science Ravensburg-Weingarten, Weingarten, Germany, patrick.striemann@hs-weingarten.de, www.hs-weingarten.de

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymers exhibit temperature-dependent material behavior. In this context, self-heating under cyclic loading significantly influences the test results, preventing a reliable evaluation of the fatigue properties. Due to the relation between the applied frequency and the resulting self-heating, the frequency resembles a critical parameter. In the current standards, the frequency is specified insufficiently, resulting in comparability issues between standard-compliant but differently performed tests. The aim of this work is to identify suitable frequencies on the basis of a newly developed energy parameter – the induced energy rate – which lead to reproducible results and thus promote comparability. The investigations were carried out on glass fiber-reinforced epoxy and polyurethane. It was shown for a defined change in temperature, that a linear relation between the maximum stress and the induced energy rate exists. On this basis, an exponential mathematical model could be determined with which suitable frequencies can be calculated. The model was successfully validated in fatigue tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

The frequency resembles a critical part in fatigue testing, because of its influence on the self-heating of the polymeric matrix material. The given standards for cyclic testing of composites and polymers define the frequency in the range of 1 to 25 Hz and a maximum of allowable temperature increase of 10 K (ISO 13003, ASTM D7791-12). However, these rules do not guarantee comparability between results of different tests. For example, it was shown for fiber-reinforced and un-reinforced polymers that the fatigue life gets prolonged with increasing frequency. These conclusions are only valid for low frequencies, e.g. 2 Hz, which do not result in any change in temperature [1, 2]. For frequencies higher than 2 Hz, the self-heating effect dominates, which reduces the fatigue life. Based on this, further studies show that a higher frequency leads to a reduction in the number of cycles to failure [3-5]. Therefore, currently, research is carried out to further investigate the frequency's influence in detail and determine optimized frequencies regarding the comparability of the test results.

However, only a few publications exist considering energy parameters. It was shown in Kang et al. and Magnabosco et al. that low induced energy meant that the tested material was able to endure higher frequencies without reaching a critical self-heating temperature [6, 7]. In further investigations [8, 9], the temperature was correlated to the intrinsic heat generation and dissipated energy, but no limiting value was identified. Bernasconi et al. related the increase of the specimen's temperature to a parameter, combining the dissipated energy and frequency, resulting in a quasi-linear relation [10].

In all studies it can be concluded that the frequency has a significant influence on the self-heating and thus on the fatigue behavior of polymer-based materials. In order to be able to evaluate and

compare the fatigue and damage behavior exactly, it is necessary to keep the self-heating as low as possible to exclude thermal damage and failure mechanisms. At the same time, it is essential to achieve identical self-heating at all stress levels in order to ensure comparability of the results.

In this study, the combined effects of the induced energy and frequency are evaluated by using a new energy approach. During this approach, a parameter – the induced energy rate – is established. The relation between induced energy rate and self-heating is investigated and integrated into stress-specific models, allowing to calculate optimized frequencies. The procedure was verified on glass fiber-reinforced epoxy (GF-EP), which is currently used in the aerospace industry, and newly developed glass fiber-reinforced polyurethane (GF-PU). The resulting frequencies were applied to investigate and compare the temperature-specific fatigue behavior.

2 THE INDUCED ENERGY RATE

The induced energy (E_{ind}) is the sum of storage energy (E_s) and loss energy (E_l) for a complete cycle, i.e. hysteresis, as shown in Fig. 1. If the viscoelasticity in an undamaged state is neglected, a linear elastic material behavior results (Eq. 2). The induced energy rate \dot{E}_{ind} is the product of the induced energy and doubled frequency (Eq. 3), and can be calculated with the given assumptions using the peak values of stress and strain (Eq. 4).

Figure 1: Separation of energies of a hysteresis.

$$E_{ind} = E_s + E_l \quad (1)$$

$$E_{ind} = E_s + E_l/2 \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{E}_{ind} = E_{ind} * 2 * f \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{E}_{ind} = [0.5 * (\sigma_{max} - \sigma_{min}) * (\epsilon_{max} - \epsilon_{min}) + \sigma_{min} * (\epsilon_{max} - \epsilon_{min})] * 2 * f \quad (4)$$

The main idea of the energy rate approach is based on the hypothesis that a constant induced energy per time unit, independent of the mechanical stress level, leads to an identical temperature increase in an undamaged state of the specimen. With this hypothesis, the associated induced energy rate can be calculated on the basis of Eq. 4 for the limit value of a permissible increase in temperature. In the following, the relationship between the induced energy rate and temperature increase is investigated in order to enable a subsequent determination of suitable frequencies.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND SCIENTIFIC STRATEGIES

The investigations were carried out on glass fiber-reinforced epoxy (GF-EP) and polyurethane (GF-PU), both with a quasi-isotropic layer setup [45F/-45F/0F/90F]_{2s} and a fiber volume of 46%. The specimens were cut by water jet cutting. The materials differ significantly in the glass transition temperature (Table 1), which is why a varying influence of the self-heating is expected. Further details on the manufacturing process and material properties can be found in [11].

Material	Glass transition temperature (°C)
Glass fiber-reinforced epoxy (GF-EP)	190
Glass fiber-reinforced polyurethane (GF-PU)	130

Table 1: Temperature-specific properties of GF-EP and GF-PU.

The tests were performed under cyclic tension-tension loading ($R = 0.1$) using a servo-hydraulic testing system (Shimadzu EHF-UV100, $F_{\max} = \pm 100$ kN) with an integrated climatic chamber. The strain was measured with a tactile extensometer (Sandner EXA 5-0.5, $l_0 = 5$ mm $\pm 10\%$) and the dynamic Young's modulus was calculated by Eq. 5. Thermocouples type K were applied in the measurement length of the tested specimen as well as on an unloaded reference specimen to exclude any influence of climatic deviations on the subsequent calculation and interpretation. The test setup is displayed in Fig. 2.

$$E_{dyn} = (\sigma_{max} - \sigma_{min}) / (\varepsilon_{max} - \varepsilon_{min}) \quad (5)$$

Figure 2: Test setup in a climatic chamber and a detailed visualization of the clamping and measurement devices.

Frequency increase tests (FIT) have been performed under various loadings (GF-EP: $\sigma_{\max} = 140$ to 260 MPa; GF-PU: 110 to 160 MPa) to determine the stress-specific relation between frequency and change in temperature. Therefore, the frequency is increased stepwise after a specific time period at constant stress amplitude (Fig. 3a). The use of constant time intervals in contrast to a concrete number of cycles serves the objective of achieving a uniform heating behavior. This means that even at high frequencies there is sufficient time to set a stable, evaluable temperature. It must be taken into account that the relative damage input is influenced by the varying number of cycles per step. To investigate the influence of climatic conditions on the relation of induced energy rate and change in temperature, the tests were carried out at low (-30 °C), room (23 °C), and elevated (70 °C) temperatures.

Figure 3: Scheme of a) frequency increase test (FIT) and b) multiple amplitude test (MAT).

Multiple amplitude tests (MAT) and constant amplitude tests (CAT) were carried out to validate the determined frequencies concerning the stress-specific change in temperature and the change in temperature until failure, respectively. In MAT, starting with $\sigma_{\max, \text{start}} = 60$ MPa, the maximum stress was increased stepwise by 20 MPa every $1E4$ cycles and the frequency was adjusted based on the determined induced energy rate. CAT were performed using constant frequencies based on the induced energy rate.

4 FREQUENCY INCREASE TESTS

Fig. 4 exemplarily shows the results of one FIT on GF-EP each for the ambient temperatures -30, 23 and 70 °C. Under constant cyclic loading of 180 MPa maximum stress, the frequency, starting with 0.5 Hz, was gradually increased by 0.5 Hz every 16.6 min ($\cong 10,000$ cycles at $f = 10$ Hz). It can be seen that the changes in temperatures for the considered ambient temperatures are proportional to the increase in frequency and attain stable phases during the steps. A significant dependence of the material behavior on the ambient temperature is recognizable. With increasing ambient temperature, a more pronounced change of the specimen temperature takes place. For the tests at 70 °C, this results in a disproportionate temperature increase beginning with 6.0 Hz and a subsequent premature failure. The determined results can be traced back to the reduction of stiffness and fatigue strength under increasing ambient temperature, which results in a greater deformation under identical stress and thus a higher energy input, leading to a more pronounced self-heating.

Figure 4: Frequency-specific change in temperature for varying ambient temperatures on GF-EP under constant cyclic maximum stress of 180 MPa.

To exclude any influence of self-heating on the fatigue properties, a low allowable limit change in temperature (ΔT_{limit}) of 2 K was defined. For GF-EP and the exemplarily maximum stress of 180 MPa (Fig. 4), this leads to frequencies of maximum 7.0 Hz (-30 °C), 5.5 Hz (23 °C), and 4.5 Hz (70 °C). For the maximum stresses given in Chapter 3 each maximum frequency for the limit change in temperature was determined.

5 INDUCED ENERGY RATE AND FREQUENCY DETERMINATION

The procedure for model-based determination of the induced energy rate and (based on this) frequency is explained below using the tests on GF-EP and GF-PU at 23 °C as an example. For the varying ambient temperatures, the procedure is analogous.

Based on the frequency data obtained in Chapter 4 and the corresponding strain measurements, the induced energy rate was calculated according to Eq. 4. In Fig. 5 the maximum stress-specific induced energy rates for GF-EP (Fig. 5a) and GF-PU (Fig. 5b) are presented. It shows that the original hypothesis regarding a constant induced energy rate must be refuted. On the other hand, there is a linear correlation, which is described by Eq. 5 and 6 with a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.92 (GF-EP) and 0.87 (GF-PU), respectively. The linear fit can therefore be used by interpolation and extrapolation to calculate the stress-specific permissible induced energy rates. In addition, it is obvious that the linear relation is significantly dependent on the material, since for GF-PU the negative slope is distinctly more pronounced.

Figure 5: Induced energy rate in relation to the maximum stress for a limit change in temperature of 2 K for a) GF-EP and b) GF-PU.

$$GF-EP \quad \dot{E}_{ind}(\sigma_{max}) = 1.21 \cdot 10^2 - 0.32 \cdot \sigma_{max} \quad (5)$$

$$GF-PU \quad \dot{E}_{ind}(\sigma_{max}) = 1.33 \cdot 10^2 - 0.55 \cdot \sigma_{max} \quad (6)$$

The permissible frequencies were then calculated according to Eq. 3 using the determined induced energy rate and induced energy. For the extrapolated ranges, the measurement results (peak values for stress and strain) of a previous MAT with constant frequency were used. The relation between frequency and maximum stress is shown in Fig. 6 and can be described by exponential fits (Eq. 7 (GF-EP) and Eq. 8 (GF-PU)). The exponential fits are applied for model-based determination of the stress-specific frequencies that lead to a temperature increase (in the stable phase and largely undamaged state) of max. 2 K, resulting in the frequencies listed in Table 2.

$$GF-EP \quad f(\sigma_{max}) = 0.3 + 27.8 \cdot e^{-(\sigma_{max} - 59.2)/14.6} + 65.0 \cdot e^{-(\sigma_{max} - 59.2)/49.3} \quad (7)$$

$$GF-PU \quad f(\sigma_{max}) = -0.6 + 38.5 \cdot e^{-(\sigma_{max} - 60.2)/35.8} + 38.6 \cdot e^{-(\sigma_{max} - 60.2)/35.8} \quad (8)$$

Figure 6: Calculated frequency in relation to the maximum stress for a limit change in temperature of 2 K for GF-EP and GF-PU.

Maximum stress (MPa)	Frequency GF-EP (Hz)	Frequency GF-PU (Hz)	Maximum stress (MPa)	Frequency GF-EP (Hz)	Frequency GF-PU (Hz)
60	90.5	76.9	160	8.7	4.2
80	49.6	43.8	180	5.8	2.2
100	30.4	24.8	200	4.0	1.0
120	19.7	14.0	220	2.8	0.3
140	13.0	7.7	240	2.1	-

Table 2: The calculated frequencies for a limit change in temperature of 2 K for GF-EP and GF-PU.

6 VALIDATION

To evaluate the procedure, MAT and CAT were performed according to the test strategy presented in Chapter 3 using the frequencies listed in Table 2.

In Fig. 7 the results of an exemplarily MAT for GF-EP are displayed. A gradual increase of the change in temperature up to 140 MPa and approx. 2 K takes place. In the following steps, the temperature remains nearly constant until an exponential increase occurs, starting at approx. 5E3 cycles in the last step ($\sigma_{\max} = 220$ MPa), which initiates the subsequent failure. The less pronounced changes in temperature during the first steps ($\sigma_{\max} = 60 - 100$ MPa) are due to the fact that with the testing system used the maximum frequency is 30 Hz and therefore the calculated frequencies, which lead to an temperature increase of 2 K, could not be reached. In all stages in which the calculated frequencies were applied, an almost identical change in temperature was achieved. Thereby an optimization of the comparability of the test results is realized, particularly in comparison to results carried out with a constant frequency, almost completely excluding thermal influences by self-heating. The exponential increase of the change in temperature is limited to a small number of cycles and can be attributed to a significant damage propagation, which is why it is to be assumed that the temperature change occurring in this case has only an insignificant influence on the number of cycles to failure.

Figure 8 presents the results of an exemplarily CAT for GF-EP with a maximum stress of 180 MPa and a calculated frequency of 5.8 Hz. The temperature increases directly with beginning of the test up to approx. 2 K and stays roughly constant until almost 4E4 cycles. Then a small and steady temperature increase occurs, which correlates with the turning point in the dynamic Young's modulus. The turning point describes an increasing material degradation, which is why an advanced damaged state (in view of critical damages) must be assumed, leading to a further change in temperature. Thereby, at approx. 7E4 cycles, the limit change in temperature is exceeded. In addition, similar to the results obtained in the MAT, a few cycles before failure an exponential increase in temperature can be detected. The results show both for MAT and CAT that the change in temperature stays more or less

constant for the whole tests independent to the maximum stress. The detected deviations are small compared to the allowable changes in temperature according to the current standards and are therefore assessed as suitable for comparability and reliability of the tests results. The exponential increase in temperature occurs just a few cycles before failure and is thus attributed to critical damage. The number of cycles to failure is therefore not significantly influenced by the temperature increase. It should also be noted that despite the exponential behavior at the end of the test, the temperature remains within the specified ranges of the standards.

Figure 7: Results of a MAT for GF-EP using calculated frequencies of 2 - 30 Hz.

Figure 8: Results of a CAT for GF-EP using a calculated frequency of 5.8 Hz.

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this study an approach for optimized frequency selection based on a new energy parameter is presented for glass fiber-reinforced epoxy and polyurethane. From the experimental results, the following can be concluded:

1. The relation of induced energy rate and maximum stress can be described by a linear function for a certain change in temperature. With an increasing maximum stress, a reduction of the induced energy rate is necessary for keeping the change in temperature constant.
2. The induced energy rate for a certain change in temperature seems to be strongly depended on the material, since epoxy and polyurethane lead to significant variations.

3. Based on the linear relation of induced energy rate and maximum stress, in combination with the peak values of strain, the stress-specific frequencies can be calculated, presenting an exponential behavior.
4. The validation shows that the change in temperature reaches the defined limit change in temperature and stays approx. constant until a few cycles before failure.

The results prove that using the new energy rate approach the comparability and reliability of test results can be improved significantly. In addition, since there is a linear relation between induced energy rate and maximum stress, in future one can manage the mathematical description with only approx. three frequency increase tests on different load levels.

In further studies, strain rate effects have to be investigated, since the varying frequencies lead to a change in strain rate, which may result in a different material behavior and therefore fatigue properties.

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